

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of organic sulfides with bis(pyridine)silver permanganate[†]

Jayshree Banerji^a, K. K. Banerji^b, Laszlo Kotai^c, Deepika Sharma^d and Pradeep K. Sharma^{*d}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, RGPM, Kolar Road, Bhopal-462 042, Madhya Pradesh, India

^bFaculty of Science, National Law University, Mandore, Jodhpur-342 304, Rajasthan, India

^cChemical Research Center, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, H-1025, Pusztaszeri u. 59-67, Budapest, Hungary

^dDepartment of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 011, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : drpkvs27@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The oxidation of organic sulfides by bis(pyridine)silver permanganate (BPSP) resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulfoxides. The reaction is first order with respect to both BPSP and sulfides. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The rate of reaction increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent. The correlation analyses of the rate of oxidation of thirty four sulfides were performed in terms of various single and multiparametric equations. The rate of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides showed excellent correlation with Charton's LDR. The rates of *ortho*-compounds showed excellent correlation with LDRS equation. The oxidation of *ortho*- and *para*-compounds is more susceptible to the delocalization effect. The *meta*-compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. The oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides exhibited a very good correlation in terms of Pavelich-Taft equation. The polar reaction constants are negative indicating an electron-deficient sulfur centre in the rate-determining step. A mechanism involving formation of a sulphonium cation intermediate in the slow step has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, permanganate.

Introduction

Bis(pyridine)silver permanganate (BPSP) is mild and selective oxidizing agent. It is found to be better reagent than potassium permanganate in many reactions, e.g. oxidative alkylamination of electron-deficient (hetero) aromatic compounds¹. We have reported its thermally induced intra-molecular redox reaction² and the oxidation of oxalic and formic acid³ with BPSP. The oxidation of organic sulfides with BPSP has not been reported, therefore, we have undertaken this work. We report here the kinetics of oxidation of 34 sulfides with BPSP in aqueous acetic acid solution. The effect of structure on the reaction rate has been analyzed and mechanistic aspects have been discussed.

Results and discussion

Oxidation of organic sulfides resulted in the formation of corresponding sulfoxides. Analysis of products and stoichiometric determination indicate the following overall reaction (1).

BPSP is reduced to Mn^{IV}. To confirm that Mn^{IV} is indeed formed as a result of reduction of BPSP by sulfides, the rate were determined by monitoring the increase in [Mn^{IV}] at 418 nm^{4,5}. The rates of decay at 529 nm and increase at 418 nm agreed within $\pm 9\%$. BPSP has virtu-

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

ally no absorption at 418 nm. This agrees with the observations of earlier workers^{4,5}.

Rate laws

The reactions are first order with respect to BPSP. Further, the values of k_{obs} , are independent of initial concentration of BPSP. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of sulfides showing that the reaction is first order with respect to sulfides also (Table 1). Fig. 1 depicts a typical kinetic run.

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. In blank experiments, with the sulfide absent, no noticeable consumption of BPSP was observed. The addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). To further confirm the

Table 1. Rate constants of the oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide with BPSP at 298 K

10^4 [BPSP] (mol dm ⁻³)	[MeSPh] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)
2.0	0.2	1.0	3.41
2.0	0.4	1.0	6.80
2.0	0.6	1.0	10.1
2.0	0.8	1.0	13.7
2.0	1.0	1.0	17.0
2.0	1.5	1.0	26.0
2.0	2.0	1.0	33.8
3.0	0.8	1.0	13.6
5.0	0.8	1.0	14.1
8.0	0.8	1.0	13.8
10.0	0.8	1.0	13.5
2.0	0.8	1.0	13.9 ^a

^aContained 0.005 mol dm⁻¹ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide by BPSP : A typical kinetic run.

absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was found that BHT was recovered unchanged almost quantitatively.

Effect of acidity : The reaction rate increases with an increase in the acidity (Table 2). A plot of rate versus [H⁺] is concave to the rate axis and makes an intercept on the rate axis (Fig. 2).

Table 2. Dependence of rate of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide with BPSP on the hydrogen-ion concentration^a

[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.7
$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)	3.84	4.35	5.38	6.05	7.52
[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	1.0	1.5	1.8	2.0	2.5
$10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)	10.1	15.8	19.3	23.0	30.6

^a 10^4 [BPSP] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³, [MeSPh] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, T = 298 K.

Fig. 2. Dependence of rate of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide by BPSP on the hydrogen ion concentration.

Effect of substituents : The rates of oxidation of a number of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides, alkyl phenyl sulfides, dialkyl sulfides and diphenyl sulfide were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3).

Effect of solvent composition : The rate of oxidation was determined in solutions containing different amounts of acetic acid and water. It was observed that the rate of oxidation increased with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent (Table 4).

There is no satisfactory correlation between the activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of sulfides with BPSP

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
(i) Substituted phenyl methyl sulfides							
H	65.0	170	425	1150	70.0 ± 1.1	-63 ± 3	88.8 ± 1.0
<i>p</i> -Me	119	306	755	1940	68.1 ± 1.0	-65 ± 4	87.3 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -OMe	224	545	1300	3340	65.7 ± 1.1	-68 ± 4	85.9 ± 1.0
<i>p</i> -F	59.1	152	378	1050	70.0 ± 1.2	-64 ± 4	89.0 ± 1.2
<i>p</i> -Cl	42.1	113	282	788	71.3 ± 1.2	-63 ± 4	89.8 ± 1.2
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	5.05	14.3	41.1	118	77.4 ± 1.0	-59 ± 3	94.8 ± 0.9
<i>p</i> -COMe	12.0	33.9	91.7	258	75.1 ± 0.9	-60 ± 2	92.8 ± 0.9
<i>p</i> -COOMe	16.9	46.4	125	354	74.4 ± 1.1	-59 ± 2	92.0 ± 1.0
<i>p</i> -Br	39.8	114	268	747	70.9 ± 1.2	-64 ± 3	89.9 ± 1.2
<i>p</i> -NHAc	127	324	784	2100	68.2 ± 1.2	-64 ± 3	87.2 ± 1.2
<i>m</i> -Me	109	279	682	1780	68.0 ± 0.9	-66 ± 3	87.5 ± 0.8
<i>m</i> -OMe	127	315	734	1860	65.2 ± 1.0	-75 ± 3	87.3 ± 1.0
<i>m</i> -Cl	24.9	66.2	168	458	71.0 ± 1.1	-68 ± 3	91.1 ± 1.1
<i>m</i> -Br	24.1	64.2	154	430	69.9 ± 1.2	-72 ± 3	91.2 ± 1.1
<i>m</i> -I	28.5	76.1	192	518	70.7 ± 0.9	-68 ± 2	90.8 ± 0.8
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	3.40	9.12	26.9	76.5	76.7 ± 1.3	-65 ± 3	95.9 ± 1.2
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	13.9	37.3	98.1	281	73.4 ± 1.3	-64 ± 3	92.5 ± 1.0
<i>o</i> -Me	26.4	71.1	184	513	72.4 ± 1.1	-63 ± 2	90.9 ± 0.9
<i>o</i> -OMe	83.0	218	541	1500	70.4 ± 1.3	-60 ± 3	88.2 ± 1.0
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	1.64	4.79	13.4	41.8	79.2 ± 1.3	-62 ± 3	97.6 ± 1.0
<i>o</i> -COOMe	3.58	10.1	27.9	84.0	77.2 ± 1.3	-63 ± 3	95.7 ± 1.2
<i>o</i> -Cl	7.67	21.1	57.1	164	74.9 ± 1.1	-64 ± 2	93.9 ± 1.0
<i>o</i> -Br	5.73	16.3	48.6	145	79.5 ± 1.2	-51 ± 3	94.5 ± 1.1
<i>o</i> -I	4.28	12.0	33.1	97.5	86.5 ± 0.9	-28 ± 3	94.7 ± 0.7
<i>o</i> -NHAc	15.6	43.1	130	345	66.9 ± 0.8	-61 ± 3	84.9 ± 0.6
<i>o</i> -F	34.5	91.8	237	663	72.1 ± 1.1	-61 ± 3	90.3 ± 1.0
<i>o</i> -CF ₃	0.79	2.41	7.02	21.7	81.2 ± 1.0	-61 ± 2	99.3 ± 0.9
<i>o</i> -CN	2.27	6.00	17.9	50.7	76.7 ± 1.3	-68 ± 3	96.9 ± 1.1
(ii) Alkyl phenyl sulfides							
Et	101	260	646	1720	69.1 ± 1.1	-63 ± 3	87.7 ± 1.1
Pr	66.8	175	444	1210	70.6 ± 1.2	-61 ± 3	88.7 ± 1.2
<i>i</i> -Pr	83.9	219	556	1500	70.4 ± 1.1	-60 ± 2	88.1 ± 1.1
<i>t</i> -Bu	26.6	76.2	209	583	75.4 ± 1.0	-52 ± 2	90.8 ± 0.9
(iii) Other sulfides							
Me ₂ S	160	412	1040	2560	67.8 ± 0.8	-63 ± 2	86.6 ± 0.6
Pr ₂ S	190	504	1250	3000	67.4 ± 0.8	-63 ± 2	86.1 ± 0.6
Ph ₂ S	28.4	74.6	227	570	74.4 ± 1.2	-55 ± 3	90.7 ± 1.1

thirty-four sulfides ($r^2 = 0.2712$), indicating the absence of a compensation effect⁶. A correlation between the calculated values of enthalpies and entropies is often vitiated by the experimental errors associated with them. The reaction, however, exhibited an excellent isokinetic rela-

tionship, as determined by Exner's method⁷. An Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9998$, slope = 0.8990 ± 0.0062) (Fig. 4). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is 675 ± 54 K. The linear isokinetic correlation

Fig. 3. Oxidation of sulfides by BPSP : Effect of temperature.

Table 4. Effect of solvent composition in the oxidation of methyl phenyl sulfide by BPSP

[BPSP] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, [Me-S-Ph] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 298 K

%AcOH	25	40	50	60	72
10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	6.12	11.7	17.0	33.3	56.7

Fig. 4. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of sulfides by BPSP.

implies that all the sulfides are oxidized by the same mechanism and the change in the rate of oxidation is governed by changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of the activation.

Solvent composition effect

The rate of oxidation increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent. This may be attributed to the change in the acidity of the medium with a change in the amount of acetic acid. Hammett's acidity function, H_0 , for low concentration of perchloric acid in a series of acetic acid-water mixtures has been determined⁸. It is observed that the acidity increases as the concentration of acetic acid increases. The present reaction is an acid-catalyzed one and with an increase in the acidity of the solution, the rate is expected to increase.

Correlation analysis of reactivity

The data in Table 4 show that the oxidation of different sulfides follows the order of their nucleophilicity: Pr₂S > Me₂S > MeSPh > Ph₂S.

Aryl methyl sulfides: The effect of structure on reactivity has long been correlated in terms of the Hammett equation⁹ or with dual substituent-parameter equations^{10,11}. In the late 1980s, Charton¹² introduced a triparametric LDR equation for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities. In this work we have applied the LDR equation [eq. (2)] to the rate constants, k_2 .

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + h \quad (2)$$

Here, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized electrical effect parameter when the active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (3).

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (3)$$

Here η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation.

For *ortho*-substituted compounds, it is necessary to account for the possibility of steric effects and Charton¹², therefore, modified the LDR equation to generate the LDRS [eq. (4)].

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + Sv + h \quad (4)$$

where v is the well known Charton's steric parameter based on Van der Waals radii¹³.

The rates of oxidation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted sulfides show an excellent correlation in terms of the LDR/LDRS equations (Table 5). All three series of aryl methyl sulfides meet the requirement of a minimum number of substituents for analysis by LDR and LDRS equations¹². We have used the standard deviation (sd), the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2), and Exner's¹⁴ parameter, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit.

The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted phenyl methyl sulfides showed that the oxidation of

Table 5. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of organic sulfides by BPSP

T (K)	L	D	R	S	η	R ²	sd	ψ	P _D	P _S
<i>para</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.38 ± 0.02	-1.58 ± 0.02	-1.46 ± 0.11	-	0.92	0.9996	0.01	0.01	53.4	-
298	-1.32 ± 0.02	-1.51 ± 0.02	-1.29 ± 0.12	-	0.85	0.9995	0.01	0.01	53.4	-
308	-1.28 ± 0.01	-1.43 ± 0.01	-1.33 ± 0.07	-	0.93	0.9997	0.01	0.01	52.8	-
318	-1.22 ± 0.02	-1.39 ± 0.02	-1.21 ± 0.12	-	0.87	0.9994	0.01	0.01	53.3	-
<i>meta</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.69 ± 0.01	-1.31 ± 0.01	-1.21 ± 0.10	-	0.92	0.9998	0.01	0.01	43.7	-
298	-1.66 ± 0.02	-1.27 ± 0.02	-1.03 ± 0.20	-	0.95	0.9995	0.02	0.01	42.2	-
308	-1.60 ± 0.02	-1.17 ± 0.02	-1.11 ± 0.20	-	0.95	0.9995	0.02	0.01	42.2	-
318	-1.55 ± 0.02	-1.12 ± 0.02	-0.93 ± 0.13	-	0.83	0.9997	0.01	0.01	41.9	-
<i>ortho</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.44 ± 0.01	-1.64 ± 0.01	-1.61 ± 0.07	1.31 ± 0.01	0.98	0.9999	0.01	0.02	53.2	29.8
298	-1.41 ± 0.02	-1.60 ± 0.01	-1.56 ± 0.14	1.26 ± 0.02	0.97	0.9997	0.01	0.01	53.1	29.5
308	-1.38 ± 0.01	-1.54 ± 0.01	-1.43 ± 0.13	1.21 ± 0.02	0.93	0.9997	0.01	0.01	52.7	29.3
318	-1.30 ± 0.02	-1.49 ± 0.02	-1.48 ± 0.16	1.18 ± 0.02	0.99	0.9996	0.01	0.01	53.0	29.7

para- and *ortho*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than to the localized effect. However, the oxidation of *meta*-substituted compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. In all cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, pointing to a decrease in selectivity with an increase in temperature.

All three regression coefficients, L, D and R, are negative indicating an electron-deficient sulfur center in the activated complex for the rate-determining step. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d , increasing the electron-donating power of the substituent and its capacity to stabilize a cationic species.

The negative value of S indicates that the reaction is subject to steric hindrance by the *ortho*-substituent. This may be the steric hindrance of the *ortho*-substituents to the approach of the oxidizing species.

The percent contribution¹² of the delocalized effect, P_D is given by following eq. (5).

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100) / (|L| + |D|) \quad (5)$$

Similarly, the percent contribution of the steric parameter¹² to the total effect of the substituent, P_S, was determined by using eq. (6).

$$P_S = (|S| \times 100) / (|L| + |D| + |S|) \quad (6)$$

Table 6. Correlation of rate of oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides with Pavelich-Taft equation^a

Temp. (K)	ρ^*	δ	R ²	sd
288	-2.36 ± 0.06	0.71 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.005
298	-2.24 ± 0.08	0.66 ± 0.01	0.9994	0.007
308	-2.19 ± 0.09	0.63 ± 0.02	0.9992	0.008
318	-2.12 ± 0.06	0.61 ± 0.01	0.9996	0.005

^aNo. of data points = 5.

The values of P_D and P_S are also recorded in Table 5. The value of P_D for the oxidation of *para*-substituted sulfides is *ca.* 53% whereas the corresponding values for the *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted sulfides are *ca.* 42 and 53% respectively. This shows that the balance of localization and delocalization effects is different for differently substituted sulfides. The less pronounced resonance effect from the *ortho*-position than from the *para*-position may be due to the twisting away of the methylthio group from the plane of the benzene ring. The magnitude of the P_S value shows that the steric effect is significant in this reaction.

In earlier studies on the oxidations of sulfides, involving a direct oxygen transfer via an electrophilic attack on the sulfide-sulfur, the reaction constants were negative but of relatively small magnitude, e.g. by hydrogen peroxide (-1.13)¹⁵, periodate (-1.40)¹⁶, permanganate (-1.52)¹⁷ and peroxydisulfate (-0.56)¹⁸. Large negative

reaction constants were exhibited by oxidations involving formation of halogeno-sulfonium cations e.g. by chloramine-T (-4.25)¹⁹, bromine (-3.2)²⁰ and *N*-bromoacetamide (-3.75)²¹. In the oxidation by *N*-chloroacetamide (NCA)²² the values of field (ρ_f) and resonance (ρ^+_R), at 298 K are -1.3 and -1.7 respectively.

Alkyl phenyl sulfides : The rates of oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides did not yield any significant correlation separately with Taft's σ^* or E_s values. The rates were therefore analyzed in terms of Pavelich-Taft's²³ dual substituent-parameter (DSP) [eq. (7)].

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (7)$$

The correlations are excellent (Table 6). Though the number of compounds is small (five) for any analysis by a DSP equation, the results can be used qualitatively. The negative polar reaction constant confirms that the electron-donating power of the alkyl group enhances the

reaction rate. The steric effect plays a minor inhibitory role.

Mechanism

In view of the absence of any effect of radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, on the reaction rate, it is unlikely that a one electron reaction giving rise to free radicals is operative in this oxidation. Theoretical calculations²⁴ have shown that there is a substantial charge transfer from the metal to the oxygen in permanganate. The most logical mode of interaction between sulfides and BPSP would, therefore, be nucleophilic attack at the metal. Donation of an unshared pair of electrons to an empty d-orbital on the metal would result in the formation of a coordinate covalent bond. The initial formed intermediate is likely to undergo a further rapid reaction in which the incipient oxide and sulfonium ions bond to form a highly structured intermediate, that would rearrange to give a sulfoxide (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The oxidation of sulfides by BPSP may involve a cyclic intermediate as has been suggested in many reactions of permanganate. The cyclic transition state will be highly strained in view of the apical position of a lone pair of electrons or an alkyl group. The steric requirements of the reaction will be higher as compared to those of reaction of Scheme 1 and the observed small magnitudes of steric reaction constants are thus consistent with the proposed acyclic mechanism. The formation of a cyclic transition state entails a more exacting specificity of orientation and should result in much larger negative entropy of activation than that observed.

Experimental

BPSP was prepared by the reported method²⁵. The sulfides were either commercial products or prepared by known methods²⁶ and were purified by distillation under reduced pressure or crystallization. Their purity was checked by comparing their boiling or melting points with their literature values. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 3 h and then fractionated. Perchloric acid (Merck) was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Product analysis : Dimethyl sulfide (0.01 mol) and BPSP (0.01 mol) were dissolved in 50 ml of 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water and the mixture was allowed to stand for *ca.* 20 h. Most of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water and extracted with chloroform (3 × 50 ml). The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate, the solvent was evaporated, and the residue was analyzed by IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The peaks were identical with those of Me₂SO. Peaks characteristics of Me₂S and MeSO₂Me could not be detected. In IR spectra, the product showed a strong and broad absorption at 1050 cm⁻¹. No band either at 1330 or 1135 cm⁻¹, characteristic of sulfones²⁷ was seen. In NMR spectroscopy, the peak due to methyl protons shifted from 2.1 ppm, in the sulfide, to 2.6 ppm in the product. In the corresponding sulfone, the peak should have appeared at 3.0 ppm²⁸.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of the sulfide (× 15 or larger) over BPSP. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, unless stated otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant tem-

perature (±0.1 K) and followed up to 80% completion by monitoring the decrease in absorption due to BPSP at 529 nm. The pseudo-first order constants, *k*_{obs}, were computed from the linear (*r* > 0.990) least-squares plots of log [BPSP] versus time plots. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that rate constants are reproducible within ±4%. Preliminary experiments showed that the oxidation is not sensitive to changes in ionic strength; therefore, no attempt was kept it constant. All kinetic measurements, except those to study acid catalysis, were performed in the absence of any added mineral acid.

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